

Review Article

Review on Factors That Affects Coffee Quality in Ethiopia

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Abstract: Arabica coffee (*Coffee Arabica* L.) is an economically important crop, which is contributing the highest of all export revenues in Ethiopia. It is also the major cash crop of the country. Despite the favorable climatic conditions, variety of coffee types and long history of its production, quality of coffee is poor due to traditional poor pre and post-harvest practices. Efforts were made so far in areas of fermentation time, drying depth, time of storage and extension support, training for coffee expertise and coffee farmers on recommended technologies. But there is lack of profound assessment works to identify the specific coffee quality problems and lack of adequate information on the effects of post-harvest processing and handling techniques on coffee quality. Therefore, this review’s objectives are assessing the impact of pre and post-harvest processing practices on the quality of both wet and dry processed coffee, identifying the inherent quality of coffee and investigating socio-economic technical and institutional factors related to coffee quality problems. From coffee farmers those factors that affect coffee quality were disease prevalence in coffee field, compost application, mixing up of differently harvested coffee during selling, availability of storage, drying materials used for drying and age of coffee in the store. Extension intervention could be the best approach to create awareness among coffee producers towards maintaining typical coffee quality profile of their garden through processing that finally adds value to their produces.

Keywords: Coffee Arabica L, Farmers, Field, Compost, Storage, Drying Materials.

1. Introduction

Coffee (*Coffee Arabica* L.) is a non-alcoholic stimulant beverage crop that belongs to the family *Rubiaceae* and genus *Coffee*. It is the only self-fertile with less than 10 per cent cross-pollination, tetraploid species ($2n=4x=44$) while others are diploids ($2n=22$) and self-incompatible (Berthaud and Charrier, 1988; Anthony *et al.*, 2001). Among 100 *Coffee* species in the genus *Coffee*; *C. Arabica* is the only species naturally occurring in Ethiopia (Anthony *et al.*, 2001; Yigzaw, 2005).

Ethiopian coffee is an important source of coffee genetic resources for the world coffee industry. As a matter of fact, Ethiopia is the only center of origin and diversity of Arabica coffee (*C. Arabica* L) (Anthony *et al.*, 2001). It is cultivated in most parts of the tropics, accounting for 80 per cent of the world coffee market, and about 70 per cent of the production (Tadesse *et al.*, 2002). It is also an important source of income

and employment in developing countries of Latin America, Africa and Asia (Anthony *et al.*, 2001).

Coffee is the major source of foreign currency for Ethiopia and contributes more than 35% of the total export earnings (FAO/WFP, 2008). Thus, it is a cornerstone in the export economy of the country and it supports directly or indirectly the livelihood of some 15 million people (EEA, 2001). Coffee, the defining feature of the national culture and identity, with 44% of the production consumed domestically (Mayne *et al.*, 2002). In Ethiopia, coffee is produced in four production systems, namely: forest, semi-forest, garden and plantation coffee in the Western, Southern, and Southwestern parts of the country (CFC, 2004). Coffee grows under diverse environmental conditions ranging from 550 m to 2600 m above sea level, with annual rainfall from 1000-2000 mm, temperature (minimum and maximum from 8-15°C, and 24-31°C, respectively), requires deep, well drained, loamy and slightly acidic soils (Paulos and Tesfaye, 2000). The estimated area of land covered by coffee is about 600,000 hectares, whereas the estimated annual national production of clean coffee is about 350,000 tons (Alemayehu *et al.*, 2008).

The genus *Coffea* consist more than one hundred different species. The species vary in terms of chemical composition (Clifford, 1985). And within *C. Arabica* the variability in quality takes a particular pattern with mutants presenting specific quality attributes such as caturra (dwarf, high productivity sometimes linked to a drop in quality) or maragotype (very large beans low Productivity but highly priced or the marked). In addition, some mutants have been identified, especially regarding low caffeine contents, such as *C. Arabica* variety Laurina (0.6% dm) and

More recently, in Brazil, an Ethiopia origin with traces of caffeine (Silvarolla *et al.*, 2004).

According to the current context of over production and low price of coffee market, improvement and valorization of coffee quality could provide the coffee chain with a new impetus. Since coffee becomes today's one of the leading marketable commodity next to oil, qualified professionals are seriously investigating the quality of coffees, because they know that the distinct flavors and character of coffee to safeguard consumers demand and interest beside today's market challenge. For example, the specialty markets of coffee are paying the premium price for the specialty preparation of coffee keeping its original types. In this regard, quality is a must that one can observe as a raw (green appearance), cup quality (smell the aroma, evaluate the body and perceive taste, flavor) and overall quality standard. Indeed, assessment of organoleptic quality is an extremely demanding exercise (Leroy *et al.*, 2006). That is, obviously important knowing the geographic and specific botanical origin of coffee for the purpose of fair international trade. This is because the origin can be used either alone or in blend imparts to the finished products on its unique sensory characteristics. Furthermore, premium price has been paid for certain origins, which also often stated on the label of coffee product (Prodoliet, 2004).

Based on the extreme demand for coffee quality to the character of those origins (types): Yirgacheffee and Sidama brands are now internationally recognized and registered as property right to Ethiopia with their distinct character/flavor and taste (IPO, 2008).

Ethiopia exports its coffee based on their areas of origin (type), which are known for their own distinct quality and agronomic characters (MoARD, 2008). The development of local landraces for each locality largely based on their yield performance and resistance to major diseases like coffee berry disease (CBD) and quality would help to reduce quality adulteration of the inherent quality of known coffees in the country. Besides genetic and environmental factors, the range of cares taken from field to cupping can affect coffee quality. In this regard, the influence of environmental factors such as soil, altitude, rainfall, and temperature as well as field management on coffee quality is scanty in most coffee growing regions of the country. Above all, the influence of harvesting, post-harvest processing and handling methods had high effects on coffee quality.

The main objective of this seminar was to review pre and post-harvesting factors that affect coffee quality in Ethiopia.

2. Discussion On The Related Research Findings

2.1. Botanical classification and characteristics

Coffee (*Coffea Arabica* L.) is the major species of the family Rubiaceae, which includes some 400 genera and 500 species, mostly trees and shrubs, mainly found in the lower regions of the tropical rainforest (Graff, 1986). The first botanical description of a coffee tree, under the name *Jasminumarabicanum*, was made in 1713 by A. de Jussieu, who studied a single plant originating from the botanic garden of Amsterdam (Graff, 1986; Wintgens, 2004). However, according to Linnaeus (1737) in Clifford and Wilson (1985), classified it as a separate genus *Coffea* with the then only one known species *C. Arabica*.

According to the review, botanists and geneticists due to the existence of diverse variability, the natural coffee populations considered as *Coffea Arabica*, *C. canephora*, *C. stenophylla*, *C. tnguebariae*, and *C. liberica* (Charier and Berthaud, 1985). But from recent commercial importance of green coffee market and production, the two species of *Coffea Arabica* and *Coffea canephora* are dominating world coffee production and marketing (Vander Vossen, 1985).

All botanists, who have explored the forests in the southwestern highlands of Ethiopia reported that the country is the center of diversity of *C. Arabica* (Sylvain, 1955; Meyer, 1965; Clifford and Wilson, 1985). It is known for the longest time and the widest spread species throughout the world, and it is evergreen, often multi stemmed shrub about 8 to 10m tall. *C. Arabica* is tetraploid ($2n = 44$) and is self-fertile (Charrier and Berthaud, 1985). Some natural cross-pollination occurs, effected by insects and wind. The ovary develops into a globular or oval drupe, normally containing two seeds. It has a length of 14-18 mm and a diameter of 10- 15 mm. It is usually called a cherry or a berry, although botanically not correctly so. The fruits take 7 to 9 months to mature. When mature, the skin is red (for some varieties yellow), covering a slipper sweet and mucilaginous pulp. Inside the fruit, the two seeds (coffee beans) lie with their flat sides together. A loose, thin and yellowish skin (parchment), with a coating of thin slimy mucilage, covers each of the two coffee beans. Underneath that skin is a thin and closely fitting membrane tegument, known as the silver skin. The beans of *C. Arabica* are 9-12 mm long, 6-7 mm wide and 3-4 mm

thick, and weigh about 0.15-0.20 g. The average weight ratio of cherries to clean coffee beans is 5.5: 1 and clean coffee contains about 2200beans per kilogram (Charrier and Berthaud, 1985; Clifford and Wilson, 1985; Graaff, 1986).

2.2. Coffee diversity

Ethiopia is the home of coffee (*Coffea Arabica* L.) and there exists extremely diverse genetic reserves in the mountain rainforests of southwest and south east of the country. About 5,800Arabica coffee accessions are conserved as *ex-situ* and 25,000 ha of forest lands have been preserved as *in-situ* forest coffee conservation (MoARD, 2008; ICO, 2004).Many important characteristics were identified in the Ethiopian Arabica coffee such as resistance to orange leaf rust (Wondimu, 1998) and coffee berry disease (Belachew et al.,2000). Variations in green bean caffeine, chlorogenicacid,and sucrose and trigonelline contents variation were also observed (Silvarolla et al., 2000). There is also variation in the size and shape, bean size, shape, color and cup quality (Wondimu, 1998). The distinct attributes such as resistant to coffee diseases, adaptable to diverse environmental conditions (drought) also indicates the existence of diverse *C. Arabica* genetic resources in the country. However, this gene pool is under serious threat mainly because of deforestation of its natural habitat for timber and food crop production and replacement of landraces by a few high yielding and diseases resistant improved varieties (Yigzaw, 2006). Thus, the Institute of Biodiversity Conservation (IBC) of Ethiopia preserved over 4500 accessions in the field as coffee gene bank on 115 ha land in Keffa, South Western part of Ethiopia (ITC, 2002).

The ex-plantation for the genotypes for the same geographical origin falling into different clusters can be found in the wild genetic divergence in the features created within each geographical zone through selection and genetic drift. Similarly, Bayetta (2001) reported that morphological variation is more important than variation in geographical origin as an indicator of genetic diversity in Ethiopian coffee. The work done by Seyoum et al. (2004) on eighty-one accessions of the Ethiopian coffee germplasm also revealed the presence of trait diversity that can be exploited in the genetic improvement of the crop through hybridization and selection.

2.3. Coffee adaptation

Adaptation of coffee landraces along topographic gradient has been studied by Taye *et al.* (2004) in Sidama and Gedeo zones, representing the major coffee growing and densely populated areas.

In the Southern Ethiopia with the respective density of 451 and 590 persons per km² (CSAE, 1998). The land is irregular as mountains, valleys, steep and gentle slope and almost flat land characterize it. According to the report, Arabica coffee landraces of these areas were known by different vernacular names (kurmie, wolisho, and deiga) that can be broadly grouped into three morphological classes. Kurmie (compact type) has small leaves, fruits, compact canopy and short height. On the other hand, wolisho (open types) has the longest leaves, fruit, bigger canopies volume, stiff stem and tallest height. Deiga (intermediate types)lies between the two classes. The study also indicates the association between plant parameters and site factors. That is, the most

recurring local coffee was the diega type in the high altitude areas of Gedeo zone where there was higher extinction rate of open wolisho and compact kurmie classes (Taye *et al.*, 2004). In addition, farmers also reported variations among these coffee landraces in yield performance, disease resistance, and quality attributes, which requires detail studies.

2.4. Coffee quality

Quality is a trait difficult to define. According to any dictionary, it is an inherent or distinguishing characteristic. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) describes quality as the ability of a set of inherent characteristics of product, system or process to fulfill requirement of customers and other interested parties (ISO, 2000). These inherent characteristics can be called “attributes”. There are different views of expressing quality. ITC (2002) defines that the quality of a parcel of coffee comes from combination of the botanical variety, topographical conditions, weather conditions, and the care taken during growing, harvesting, storage, export preparation and transport. On the other hand, for coffee, the definition of quality and the attributes considered have probably evolved through the centuries. Now a days, according to Lorey *et al.* (2006), this definition varies along the production to consumer chain.

At the farmer level: coffee quality is combination of production level, price and easiness of culture; at the exporter or importer level: coffee quality is linked to bean size, lack of defects, regularity of provisioning, tonnage available, physical characteristics and price; at the roaster level: coffee qualities depend on moisture content, stability of the characteristics, origin, price, biochemical.

Compounds and organoleptic quality. It should be noted that each consumer market or country may define its own organoleptic qualities; at the consumer level: coffee quality deal with price, taste and flavor, effect on health and alertness, geographical origin, environmental and sociological.

Zxe3Aspects (organic coffee, fair trade, etc.) (Lorey *et al.*, 2006).

2.5. Factors Affecting Coffee Quality

Cup quality is a complex characteristic which depends on a series of factors such as the species or variety (genetic factors), environmental conditions (ecological factors), agronomical practices (cultivation factors), processing systems (post-harvest factors), storage conditions, industrial processing, preparation of the beverage and taste of the consumer (Moreno *et al.*, 1995). Coffee quality is of critical importance to the coffee industry. Quality coffee is a product that has desirable characteristics such as clean raw and roasted appearance, attractive aroma and good cup taste (Behailu *et al.*, 2008).

However, in Ethiopia the quality of coffee produced by farmers has been deteriorating from time to time. Moreover, factors that determine coffee quality are genotypes, climatic conditions, and soil characteristics of the area, agronomic practices, harvesting methods and timing, post-harvest processing techniques, grading, packing, storage conditions and transporting, all contribute either exaltation or deterioration of coffee (Behailu *et al.*, 2008). Similarly, Damanu (2008), reported coffee quality as a

combination of the botanical variety, topographical conditions, and climatic conditions and the care taken during growing, harvesting, storage, exports preparation and transport. According to the review botanical variety and topographical conditions are constant and therefore dominate the inherent characters of a coffee where as other factors except climatic conditions can be influenced by human being and are a key factor in determination of the end quality of a green coffee. Furthermore, inadequate systems of harvesting, processing, storage and transportation are responsible for the wide spread failure to maintain the inherent quality of coffee produced in Ethiopia (Alemayehu *et al.*, 2008).

Figure 1. Schematic presentation of the major factors influencing coffee quality and their interactions in Ethiopia. Source. African journal of agricultural research

2.6. Climatic and soil factors

The environment has also a strong influence on coffee quality (Decasy *et al.*, 2003). Altitude, daily temperature fluctuations, amount and distribution of rainfall and the physical and chemical characteristics of the soil are very important factors. Climate, altitude, and shade play an important role through temperature, availability of light and water during the ripening period (Decasy *et al.*, 2003). Rainfall and sunshine distributions have a strong influence on flowering, bean expansion, and ripening (Harding *et al.*, 1987). The slowed-down ripening process of coffee berries at higher elevations (lower air temperatures), or under shading, allows more time for complete bean filling (Vaast *et al.*, 2006), yielding beans that are denser and far more intense in flavor than their neighbors grown at lower altitudes (or under full sunlight). The slower maturation process should therefore play a central role in determining high cup quality, possibly by guaranteeing the full manifestation of all biochemical steps required for the development of the beverage quality (Silva *et al.*, 2005). For instance, chromogenic acids and fat content have been found to increase with elevation in *C. Arabica* (Bertrand *et al.*, 2006). Besides the beneficial effect of longer duration of the

bean-filling period, a larger leaf area-to-fruit ratio (better bean filling capacity) may also be linked to superior cup quality (Vaastet *et al.*,2006).

The role of soil types has been well studied and it is generally admitted that the most acidic coffee quality is grown on rich volcanic soils (Harding *et al.*, 1987). The perceived acidity of coffee brews has always been recognized as an important attribute of coffee quality. Acidity is typically a highly valued quality especially in Central American and some East African coffees (Yigzaw, 2005). Sourness, however, is an extreme of acidity and can be considered as defect. Acidity has been correlated with coffees grown at very high altitudes and in mineral rich volcanic soils. On top of this Yigzaw (2005) reported that if other factors are kept constant, better quality coffee can be found at higher altitudes, while low land coffee were found to be somewhat bland, with considerable body. Moreover, coffee from high altitude areas was more acidic, with better aroma and flavor.

Woe lore (1993) reported that for Ethiopian conditions an underwater fermentation technique and the time for fermentation for different agro-ecologies are recommended. According to the review mucilage degradation washed at the first, second, third, or after the third day from pulping in the altitudinal range 1200 m and below, 1200-1500 m,1500-1800 m and above 1800 m, respectively, for varying fermentation practices. Woe lore (1995) reported that factors such as total rainfall, relative humidity, maximum-minimum temperatures with effect on water vapor content of the air and storage duration, greatly influence storability and quality of stored parchment coffee. Periods of prolonged drought may also result in lower quality beans (Wintgens, 2004). Most of the coffee tasters agree now that there is very little or no difference in flavor at all between the Arabica purebreds cultivated under similar agro-climatic conditions (Wintgens, 2004).

There was a positive and significant relationship between minimum temperature and coffee aroma. This may be because climate is an important factor with considerable effect on soil properties and thus important factor for coffee quality. It affects the rate of soil formation especially temperature and rainfall and the type of soil that is ultimately formed by influencing weathering processes.

The climate also affects the type of vegetation it supports by influencing the physiology of plants such as photosynthesis, flowering, maturity, etc., which has implications on coffee quality. This is very interesting in the context of current global climate change. The influence of rainfall on cup quality was not as apparent as that of its effect on bean size distribution. In general, the higher the rainfall, the higher the proportion of smaller beans and vice versa.

2.7. Pre-harvest and harvest factors

Yigzaw (2005) reported that in South America, coffee grown with heavy application of nitrogen fertilizer had poorer, lighter and thinner quality than that from unfertilized fields. An excess of nitrogen increase the caffeine content, resulting in a more bitter taste of the brew. The caffeine and chlorogenic acid contents of the beans are not affected by the levels of phosphorus, calcium, potassium and magnesium in the soil (Wintgens, 2004). A lack of zinc will lead to the production of small light grey-colored beans, which will produce poor liquor (Wintgens, 2004). On the other hand,

magnesium deficiency had an adverse effect on cup quality (Mitchell, 1988). High concentration of calcium (>0.11%) and potassium (>1.75%) in the beans is associated with a bitter and “hard” taste (Wintgens, 2004). Teye(1998) reported the use of decomposed coffee husk at a rate of 10 ton ha⁻¹ (4 kg tree⁻¹ on dry weight basis) was found to be superior in terms of yield performance of coffee trees.

A significant improvement in growth and yield of mature coffees was reported in response to coffee pulp and husk compost application (Chane, 1999). On the other hand, there is no correlation between the phosphorus content and the physical and organoleptic quality of the bean (Wintgens, 2004). On the contrary, repeated application of elephant grass or livestock manure resulted in an increased percentage of undesirable brown-colored bean and, thus, poor roasting characteristics. This effect was associated with a magnesium deficiency induced by the high potassium content of elephant grass as well as high concentration of potassium and calcium in manure (Wintgens, 2004).

Good growth conditions (weed control, appropriate planting density and pruning) usually have apposite effect on bean size and flavor (Wintgens, 2004).

The relationship between crop management and total coffee quality, however, has not yet been investigated in detail.

According to the review, (Bertrand *et al.*, 2006; Vaast *et al.*, 2006), tree physiology, plant age, and period of picking all interact to produce the final characteristics of the product. Indeed it was found that tree age, location of the fruits within the tree, and fruits-to-leaves ratio had a strong influence on the chemical content of green beans. Maturation also has a strong influence on coffee quality.

The main factor affecting natural coffee quality is harvesting method. It is widely agreed that traditional hand-picking and husbandry labor, as opposed to mechanical harvest, produce the best quality green coffee by decreasing the percentage of defects in coffee batches. Bertrand *et al.* (2006) observed that yellow or green cherries picked at the end of the picking season contain beans with a higher maturity level than red cherries of *C. canephora* picked at the start of the picking season. This can be seen in bean size, chemical contents, and cup quality. On the other hand, for *C. Arabica* in Costa Rica, early picking of red cherries gives the best coffee (Bertrand *et al.*, 2006).

On the other hand, Endale *et al.* (2008) pointed out that low caffeine content were found in bean harvested at immature stage (unripe) and in over-ripe coffee beans with conventional analysis using high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). According to the review, this could be associated with slow metabolism of caffeine and its biodegradation at immature and over-ripe stages of fruit development, respectively.

2.8. Post-harvest factors

Depending on the post-harvest processes, significant effects on coffee quality can be observed (Barel and Jacquet, 1994). Processing is a very important activity in coffee production and plays a crucial role in quality determination (Mburu, 1999). Coffee is either processed by the wet or dry methods, which vary in complexity and expected quality of the coffee (Wrigley, 1988). Both sun-drying as well as wet-processing

methods are operated in Ethiopia, which accounts for 70% and 30% of coffee produced in the country, respectively (Jacquet *et al.*, 2008).

According to Clifford (1985) wet processed Arabica is aromatic with fine acidity and some astringency, while dry processed Arabica is less aromatic and less acidic but with greater body. The Perceived acidity of washed coffees is also significantly higher than the acidity found in naturally(dry) processed coffees. This is likely due to an increase in the body of naturally processed coffees relative to wet processed coffees since body masks the coffee's acidity (Yigzaw, 2005). Selmar *et al.* (2001) reported that sensory evaluation of the roast coffees revealed that the dry and washed.

Coffees could be distinguished with high significance (11 of 11 panel members). As their report the differences in quality of differently processed coffees of similar original material is due to the process taking place in the beans during processing.

The second method is the wet processing method in which the fresh red cherries are processed in three stages i.e. removals of the pulp and mucilage, fermentation and washing, and drying of parchment coffee (CFC, 2004). The covering period during drying and depth of parchment layer affects the total time required to dry parchment coffee to an optimum moisture level. Solomon and Behailu (2006) identified parchment coffee dried at the highest drying depth (5 cm) gave the lowest Value of cup quality, while the other drying depths (2, 3 and 4 cm) gave better values of cup quality. Then, parchment coffee is dried and ready for transport to where it is sold in the auctions (still in parchment form). Concerning its marketing, all Ethiopian export coffee has to be channeled through the central auctions in Addis Ababa (CFC, 2004).

In washed coffee production, final quality among others is greatly dependent upon the fermentation process (Woelore, 1993). It has been confirmed that under-water soaking following 'dry' fermentation, i.e., two-stage fermentation enhances the appearance of both raw and roast coffees compared to 'dry' fermentation only (Behailu *et al.*, 2008). According to this review post fermentation soaking for 24 hours produced better raw and roast appearance than either 8 or 16 hours soaking but extending the soak to 48 hours did not cause any further improvement to the raw and actually reduced the roast quality.

2.9. Genetic factors

As harvesting method, post-harvest procedures and the physiology of the plant itself affect coffee quality, its genetic origin (species and genotype) also greatly influence coffee quality (Leroy *et al.*, 2006). Agwanda (1999) compared four traits (acidity, body, and flavor) and overall standard for their suitability as selection criteria for the genetic improvement of overall liquor quality. According to the review, based on correlation, repeatability and sensitivity analysis, flavor rating. Was recommended as the best selection criterion for genetic improvement of cup quality in Arabica coffee. The trait showed high genetic correlation with preference, was easy to determine organoleptic ally and had relatively high sensitivity in discriminating different coffee genotypes. Yigzaw (2005) also revealed that coffee quality depends on genetic make-up and genes control the production of chemical compounds that behave as aroma agents either directly or as aroma precursors expressed during the roasting process.

Hence while selecting a cultivar to be planted; cup quality must be the first priority to be considered.

Furthermore, Owuor (1988) and Moreno *et al.* (1995) improved the cup quality of different coffee genotypes with the assistance of professional coffee tasters. Close similarity among liquorers in ranking various cup quality characteristics of the cultivars, indicating that any one panel could be relied on selection for cup quality. Similarly, Agwanda *et al.* (2003) reported significant genotype x environment interaction effects on coffee bean and liquor quality. Walyaro (1983) reported relatively lower genotype x environment interaction effects on quality characters.

On the contrary, Van der Vossen (1985) reported non-significant genotype x environment interaction effects on quality characters, such as bean size and cup quality. The genotype is a key factor, since it determines to a great extent important characteristics such as the size and shape of the beans as well as their color, chemical composition and flavor (Wintgens, 2004). The shape and structure of beans (elephant, pea bean and empty beans) are the result of both genotype and environmental factors (Wintgens, 2004).

Table 1. Variation of chemical components of green beans in *C. Arabica* and *C. canephora*.

Component	C. Arabica	C. canephora
pH	5.26-6.11	5.27-6.13
Mineral content *	3.5-4.5	3.9-4.5
Fat content *	13-17	7.2-11
Caffeine content *	0.7-2.2 (average 1.4)	1.5-2.8 (average 2.2)
Chlorogenic acids content	4.80-6.14	5.34-6.41
Trigonelline*	1- 1.2	0.6-1.7
Oligosaccharides*	6 – 8	5 – 7
Total polysaccharides*	50 – 55	37 – 47

* % dry matter (dm) Source: (Wintgens, 2004)

(Source Braz. J. Plant Physiol., 18(1):229-242, 2006)

3. Conclusion

Arabica coffee (*Coffea Arabica* L.) is an economically important crop, which is contributing the highest of all export revenues in Ethiopia. Coffee being the major cash crop and serves as a major means of income for the livelihood of coffee farming families.

Despite the favorable climatic conditions, variety of local coffee types for quality improvement and long history of coffee production quality of the crop is poor due to traditional and poor pre and post-harvest practices, which are still used by majority of the farmers, where the bulk of the production comes from.

Cup quality is a complex characteristic which depends on a series of factors such as species or variety (genetic factors), environmental conditions (ecological factors), agronomic practices (farm management), processing systems (post-harvest factors), storage conditions, preparation of the beverage and taste/preference of the consumer.

Consequently, coffee quality is the product of many environmental and anthropogenic factors acting together and hence yielding coffees of different quality with their own unique characteristics.

Recommendations

In order to produce quality coffee, smallholder farmers should undertake the following agronomic and post-harvest handling practices given as advice.

- Use the recommended seedling or planting materials.
- Improve coffee tree management practices.
- For old aged coffee, use stumping to rejuvenate the coffee tree.
- Apply fertilizers and compost to their coffee fields adequately.
- Improve harvesting practice by harvest red ripen cherries by hand-picking.
- Practice sorting after harvesting before drying.
- Should differentiate price based on the quality of the coffee.
- Keep the quality of collected coffee by storing at safe places and collectors should avoid mixing of foreign matters with coffee.

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